

ENHANCING FUTSAL TRAINING: AN EVALUATION OF CREATIVE 3H SESSION GUIDE

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ABSTRACT

The aim of the study is to evaluate the Creative 3H Session Guide for Futsal Training. After the district implementation of the Creative 3H Session Guide, it is but proper to seek the evaluation of the MAPEH Teachers and Coaches who attended the event. To join the MATATAG agenda of DepEd, particularly in making the curriculum relevant, the researcher studied the effectiveness of the session guide which will be officially used in Futsal Training. The researcher asked the MAPEH teachers and coaches to evaluate the session guide using a researcher-made survey questionnaire. Employing a descriptive quantitative method, the study found that the respondents perceived that the Creative 3H Session Guide was effective and efficient. The Weighted Mean shows that the respondents strongly agree that the material was adequate, coherent, appropriate, and useful. Therefore, it is recommended that the material be implemented again. This study was used to evaluate and improve the Creative 3H Session Guide. The guide will be used by the students who will take part in Futsal Sports.

Keywords: *Creative 3H, Futsal Training, Futsal Guide, San Mateo District, Division of Rizal*

INTRODUCTION

In the world of education and sports development, it is important to use creative methodologies in forming the potentials of student athletes. An example of such an

endeavor is the Creative 3H Camp, a pilot simulation program led by the Division of Rizal. This initiative is founded on the dedication to enriching the educational encounters of students within the context of the K to 12 curriculum. Its objective is to refine and supplement essential domains and competencies, such as Societal Engagement, Technical Skills, Social Skills, and the guidance outlined in Division Memorandum no. 301, s.2023, which promotes a division crash course in sports coaching and officiating.

The Creative 3H Camp was organized by the San Mateo Sub-Office in 2023, with the primary objective of enhancing the quality of futsal instruction. This research study looked at the results of the aforementioned effort, analyzing its alignment with the four fundamental principles of access, equity, quality, and resiliency and well-being. Moreover, this study determined the incorporation of this inquiry into the facilitating mechanisms of the Regional Education Development Plan (REDP), Division Education Development Plan (DEDP), School Improvement Plan (SIP), or Annual Investment Plan (AIP). Specifically, the emphasis is placed on establishing fundamental principles and addressing pressing issues in the realm of sports education.

Moreover, this study identifies a correlation with the DepEd MATATAG goal, which aims to enhance the curriculum's applicability in order to cultivate capable and employment-ready individuals who are engaged and accountable members of society. Additionally, the objective of this initiative is to expedite the provision of fundamental educational infrastructure and services, foster the welfare of students, encourage inclusive education practices, cultivate a conducive learning atmosphere, and offer crucial assistance to educators in order to enhance their instructional approaches.

The research bids the Division or School Learning Recovery Plan (SLRP) for the academic year 2022-2023, focusing on the significance of innovative sports programs in promoting the comprehensive recovery and development of students, alongside existing national-level initiatives. It aimed to identify the evaluation of the MAPEH teachers and coaches on the Creative 3H Camp in strengthening futsal training and its contribution towards educational and athletic advancement. By conducting a thorough assessment, the researcher aims to ascertain the importance of this project in influencing the trajectory of the students and athletes, and thus, the trajectory of the division of Rizal.

MAPEH teachers and coaches play a crucial role in ensuring an enabling and supportive environment and materials for effective teaching and learning of the different knowledge and skills in sports. Through their quality teaching and review of the curriculum and materials, the Department of Education can develop quality session guide so that the department may have "holistic learners who are steeped in values, equipped with 21st century skills, and able to propel the country to development and progress (DepEd Order no. 42, s.2017). Yangkara et al. (2024) tested a physical training model on futsal players based on circuit training which was found feasible and applicable while Apriantono et al. (2023) found that speed training on the physical performance of futsal players is effective. The current study wanted to test the acceptability of futsal training as well used in the district of San Mateo.

Asshagab et al. (2020) identified Futsal as a sport that has a resemblance to conventional football, but with some fundamental skills that diverge, particularly for young players. The individual need a recreational activity that is both enjoyable and easily comprehensible, devoid of the requirement for written explanations or theoretical frameworks. The findings of this investigation indicated a lack of a standardized guide and little diversity in the types of games played in futsal. The activity remains traditional. In order to effectively engage in futsal, students must acquire fundamental methods by using workout concepts, employing a diverse range of games, and executing proper movement mechanics (Asshagab, 2020). This study is particularly relevant to the current study as the latter heeded the call to draft a futsal training guide.

Salino et al. (2022) investigated how engagement in sports among students has been found to have a positive impact on their overall health. Athletes, who regularly participate in sports activities, tend to exhibit higher levels of physical fitness and overall well-being compared to their non-athlete counterparts. Additionally, these students often display increased levels of physical activity, self-confidence, and enthusiasm. It evaluated the degree of sufficiency of sports facilities, equipment, and sports performance in the public high schools within the Tinambacan District of the Schools Division of Calbayog City. The findings showed a persistent shortage of MAPEH educators at educational institutions, inadequate financial resources allocated to sports, the establishment of sports clubs, and the implementation of sports development initiatives. However, a significant majority of their athletes have engaged in regional and national sporting contests. There exists a clear correlation between the performance of athletes and the quality of sports facilities and equipment. Consequently, the researcher proposes an enhancement of the athletic development program, together with a heightened emphasis on the comprehensive development of the learners (Salino, 2022).

Florentino (2023) used a self-administered questionnaire to gather data from a total of 342 stakeholders pertaining to their demographic characteristics, their level of awareness and comprehension regarding the goals and objectives of their athletic program, and their willingness to endorse the program. The findings indicated that stakeholders exhibited a reasonable degree of awareness, acceptability, and comprehension of the program's goals and objectives. It was observed that internal stakeholders, overall, demonstrated a better level of understanding compared to external stakeholders. The study's findings indicate a necessity for enhancing communication and collaboration between the program and external stakeholders to enhance their comprehension and endorsement of the program's goals and objectives. The results of this study can be utilized as a foundation for conducting formative curriculum evaluation and enhancing the curriculum, hence facilitating the program's ability to effectively address the requirements of both students and the industry (Florentino, 2023).

Pambudi et al. (2021) studied the influence of training methods and agility towards futsal dribbling speed result. Their findings showed that there was an interaction between training methods and agility towards the dribbling speed in high school male futsal players and there was a different influence between the high and low agility towards the dribbling speed in high school male futsal players. There was an interaction between training

methods and agility towards the dribbling speed in high school male futsal players. Prasetya et al. (2021) produced a model on basic technique skills training for passing and shooting futsal which was found effective and feasible. Rozi et al. (2023) found that imagery and agility exercises can improve the reaction time of futsal goal keeper. Febrinaldo and Ihsan (2023) added that apart from imagery, self-confidence is important in futsal shooting results. Sari et al. (2024) provided that plyometric training, body weight training, and paying attention to explosive power factors improves the explosive power of futsal players' legs.

Research Questions

The following are the specific questions that this research answered:

1. What was the evaluation of MAPEH teachers and coaches on the developed 3H Session Guide in terms of;
 - a. Adequacy;
 - b. Coherence;
 - c. Appropriateness; and
 - d. Usefulness?
2. What recommendations did the respondents give for the improvement of the session guide?
3. Based on the findings of the study, what enhancements can be formulated to enhance the 3H Session Guide in the District of San Mateo?

METHODOLOGY

The research sought the evaluation of Junior High School MAPEH teachers and coaches on the developed 3H Session in the District of San Mateo for the school year 2022-23. The study included the 12 MAPEH Teachers and Coaches who joined the Creative 3H Session and answered the evaluation survey. The study utilized the mixed method of research where both qualitative and quantitative approaches were applied. Taherdoost (2022) explained that mixed-method methods simply employ a combination of both qualitative and quantitative approaches based on the purpose of the study and the nature of the research question aiming to provide a better understanding of the subject.

On quantitative approach, a survey questionnaire based on the Validation Checklist in Session Guide was utilized for gathering the data to find out the evaluation of the 3H Session Guide as perceived by the MAPEH teachers and coaches with respect to adequacy, coherence, appropriateness, and usefulness. The questionnaire is researcher-made and was validated by 3 master teachers on MAPEH in the district of San Mateo. It was pilot tested to MAPEH teachers who are not part of the study and the internal consistency was calculated using Cronbach's Alpha which yielded a .920 result, verbally interpreted as excellent. The Likert scale used for the survey is the following:

Likert Scale	Scale	Verbal Interpretation
5	4.21-5.00	Strongly Agree
4	3.41-4.20	Agree
3	2.61-3.40	Neutral
2	1.81-2.60	Disagree
1	1.00-1.80	Strongly Disagree

On the other hand, qualitative approach was employed through the solicitation of the respondents' comments and suggestions of the 3H Camp. Thematic approach was employed in which the responses are grouped according to common themes and sub-themes for an organized presentation of comments and suggestions.

RESULTS

1. Evaluation of the Respondents:

Adequacy of the Creative 3H Session Guide

Table 1: Weighted Mean for the Adequacy of the Creative 3H Session Guide

ADEQUACY	WM	INTERPRETATION
Instruction corresponds with activities	4.58	Strongly Agree
Learning activities satisfy the stated objectives	4.58	Strongly Agree
Provides independent activities	4.50	Strongly Agree
Evident graphical and pictorial images	4.50	Strongly Agree
Concepts presented logically	4.50	Strongly Agree
General WM	4.53	Strongly Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.80 strongly disagree, 1.81- 2.60 disagree, 2.61-3.40 neutral, 3.41-4.20 agree, 4.21- 5.00 strongly agree

The assessment of the "Creative 3H Session Guide" yields a predominantly favorable evaluation across multiple parameters. The efficacy of the guide is evidenced by its consistently elevated weighted mean scores, all of which are situated inside the "Strongly Agree" category. The consensus among users is that there is a high level of agreement regarding the tight correspondence between the instructions provided and the activities undertaken, suggesting a smooth and harmonious alignment between the assistance offered and its practical implementation. Moreover, the learning activities delineated in the guide are often regarded as highly effective in attaining their intended goals.

Moreover, the incorporation of autonomous learning tasks is highly valued, enhancing the opportunity for self-guided educational engagement. The utilization of conspicuous graphical and pictorial representations augments user involvement, while ideas are conveyed in a rational and cohesive fashion. Taken together, the results indicate that the Creative 3H Session Guide demonstrates exceptional performance in providing a high-quality educational encounter, as evidenced by the average weighted

score of 4.53 falling inside the "Strongly Agree" category. The Creative 3H Session Guide has gotten a consistently positive overall rating in the "Strongly Agree" category, indicating that it is highly regarded and strongly recommended for its effectiveness.

Coherence of the Creative 3H Session Guide

Table 2: Weighted Mean for the Coherence of the Creative 3H Session Guide

COHERENCE	WM	INTERPRETATION
Activities conform with the concepts	4.58	Strongly Agree
Contains relevant activities	4.50	Strongly Agree
Provides relevant information for better understanding	4.50	Strongly Agree
Activities develop creativity and resourcefulness	4.42	Strongly Agree
General WM	4.50	Strongly Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.80 strongly disagree, 1.81- 2.60 disagree, 2.61-3.40 neutral, 3.41-4.20 agree, 4.21- 5.00 strongly agree

The assessment of the "Creative 3H Session Guide" lays significant importance on the guide's coherence, assessing the degree to which its contents and activities are aligned to promote efficient learning. The information displayed in Table 2, which includes weighted mean scores, indicates a significantly positive evaluation across multiple areas. The scores obtained reflect the users' high level of agreement about the guide's cohesiveness and its effectiveness in delivering a well-organized learning experience.

The criterion of "Activities conforming with the concepts" had a notable score of 4.58, falling under the "Strongly Agree" category. This suggests that the respondents observed a notable correspondence between the activities presented in the guide and the underlying principles it seeks to communicate. The establishment of this alignment is crucial in facilitating learners' ability to effectively integrate theoretical knowledge with practical application.

Another crucial component, "Includes pertinent activities," also received a good score of 4.50 within the "Strongly Agree" category. This highlights the effectiveness of the guide in providing activities that directly support the achievement of educational goals. Concurrently, the guide demonstrates proficiency in "facilitating the comprehension of pertinent information," as evidenced by a corresponding rating of 4.50 within the "Strongly Agree" category. This implies that the guide proficiently provides learners with the requisite knowledge to improve their understanding.

Moreover, the guide is perceived as fostering creativity and resourcefulness, as evidenced by a rating of 4.42 under the "Strongly Agree" category for the criterion "Activities that cultivate creativity and resourcefulness." In conclusion, the aforementioned data emphasize the strong coherence and alignment between the Creative 3H Session Guide and its intended aims. The platform provides pertinent exercises, imparts crucial knowledge for comprehension, and cultivates originality and ingenuity.

Appropriateness of the Creative 3H Session Guide

Table 3: Weighted Mean for the Appropriateness of the Creative 3H Session Guide

ADEQUACY	WM	INTERPRETATION
Based on the MELC learning competencies	4.58	Strongly Agree
Arranged in the correct sequence	4.50	Strongly Agree
Provides immediate needs	4.42	Strongly Agree
Provides varied activities to sustain interest	4.42	Strongly Agree
Adapted to intended learners	4.33	Strongly Agree
General WM	4.45	Strongly Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.80 strongly disagree, 1.81- 2.60 disagree, 2.61-3.40 neutral, 3.41-4.20 agree, 4.21- 5.00 strongly agree

The assessment of the "Creative 3H Session Guide" focuses significant importance on its suitability for its designated objective and intended recipients. Table 3 presents the weighted mean scores, providing valuable insights into the applicability and relevance of the guidance. The efficacy of a learning resource is heavily dependent on its appropriateness, and the data provided highlights the guide's strong alignment in this aspect.

The criterion "Based on the MELC learning competencies" obtained a significantly high score of 4.58 falling inside the "Strongly Agree" category. This indicates that users exhibit a high level of agreement with the guide's seamless alignment with the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELC), hence suggesting its suitability for fulfilling educational standards and objectives. In addition, the criterion pertaining to the arrangement of content in the correct sequence received a noteworthy score of 4.50 within the "Strongly Agree" category. This result underscores the effective structure and logical progression of the guide.

Furthermore, the guide is widely regarded as being highly effective in meeting immediate requirements and maintaining student engagement, as evidenced by the ratings of 4.42 in the "Strongly Agree" category for both "Provides immediate needs" and "Provides varied activities to sustain interest." Furthermore, the adaptation of the material to the specific needs and characteristics of the intended learners, as evidenced by a score of 4.33 in the "Strongly Agree" category for "Adapted to intended learners," serves as a testament to its appropriateness for the designated target audience. The Creative 3H Session Guide demonstrates a high level of appropriateness, as evidenced by the overall weighted mean score of 4.45 in the "Strongly Agree" category. This score indicates that the guide aligns well with competencies, exhibits effective organization, addresses immediate needs, promotes engagement, and facilitates learner adaptation.

Thus, the analysis reveals that the Creative 3H Session Guide demonstrates exceptional appropriateness, indicating its congruence with learning characteristics. Furthermore, it exhibits good organization, relevance to urgent requirements, engagement through a diverse range of activities, and adaptability to the intended

learners. The guide's remarkable appropriateness highlights its ability to offer a highly relevant and successful learning experience for its intended audience.

The Usefulness of the Creative 3H Session Guide

Table 4: Weighted Mean for the Usefulness of the Creative 3H Session Guide

USEFULNESS	WM	INTERPRETATION
Easy to understand	4.67	Strongly Agree
Serves as an instructional tool	4.67	Strongly Agree
Provides knowledge and skills	4.42	Strongly Agree
Encourages creative and critical thinking	4.42	Strongly Agree
General WM	4.60	Strongly Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.80 strongly disagree, 1.81- 2.60 disagree, 2.61-3.40 neutral, 3.41-4.20 agree, 4.21- 5.00 strongly agree

This evaluation revolves around the guide's primary characteristic: usefulness. This assessment critically examines the guide's use and efficacy in promoting learning, rendering it an essential component of its overall caliber. The information displayed in Table 3, which includes weighted mean scores, provides a comprehensive representation of the effectiveness of the guide across several aspects.

The criterion of "Ease of understanding" gives a noteworthy score of 4.67, falling into the range of "Strongly Agree." The outstanding rating indicates that users highly agree with the guide's ability to effectively deliver material in a clear manner, hence ensuring accessibility for learners with varying levels of expertise. Concurrently, the statement "Serves as an instructional tool" has a noteworthy rating of 4.67 under the "Strongly Agree" category, confirming the guide's efficacy as a powerful tool in facilitating the educational process.

In addition, the guide has been widely regarded as a highly successful tool in facilitating the acquisition of knowledge and skills, as well as fostering the development of creative and critical thinking abilities. This is evident from the average rating of 4.42, which falls into the "Strongly Agree" category. This highlights the significance of its function as a comprehensive educational tool that not only conveys fundamental knowledge and skills, but also encourages learners to engage in critical and creative thinking. The Creative 3H Session Guide demonstrates significant utility, as seen by the weighted mean score of 4.60 in the "Strongly Agree" category. The consensus among users is that the tool demonstrates exceptional proficiency in providing lucidity, serving as an effective instructional aid, conveying knowledge and competencies, and fostering cognitive development by stimulating creative and critical thinking.

As a result, the analysis highlights the remarkable utility of the guide. The consensus among users is that the platform demonstrates a high level of proficiency in efficiently conveying information, functioning as a potent tool for training, effectively imparting knowledge and skills, and nurturing the development of creative and critical thinking abilities. The guide's demonstrated high degree of utility serves to reinforce its

capacity to greatly enhance the educational experience, equip learners with vital skills, and foster comprehensive cognitive growth.

The Overall Weighted Mean of Creative 3H Session Guide
Table 5: Overall Weighted Mean

Creative 3H Session Guide	WM	Interpretation
Adequacy	4.53	Strongly Agree
Coherence	4.50	Strongly Agree
Appropriateness	4.45	Strongly Agree
Usefulness	4.60	Strongly Agree
	4.52	Strongly Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.80 strongly agree, 1.81- 2.60 disagree, 2.61-3.40 neutral, 3.41-4.20 agree, 4.21- 5.00 strongly agree

The entire assessment of the Creative 3H Session Guide's performance across essential aspects, namely Adequacy, Coherence, Appropriateness, and Usefulness, is presented in Table 5 through the "Overall Weighted Mean." The weighted mean (WM) of 4.52, which falls inside the "Strongly Agree" category, indicates a collective expression of high agreement among users recognizing the excellent quality and effectiveness of the guide.

In the category of Adequacy, the guide obtains a weighted mean (WM) score of 4.53, which signifies a high level of consensus among users on its alignment with instructional objectives, coherent presentation of content, encouragement of individual learning, and inclusion of stimulating activities. Additionally, the areas of Coherence, Appropriateness, and Usefulness also received high ratings of "Strongly Agree" from the participants, with mean scores of 4.50, 4.45, and 4.60, respectively. The evaluation highlight the guide's notable coherence, appropriateness for its intended purpose and target audience, and effectiveness in promoting learning through clear communication, instructional usefulness, the transmission of knowledge and skills, and the stimulation of critical and creative thinking.

The Creative 3H Session Guide demonstrates exceptional performance, as indicated by its Overall Weighted Mean of 4.52. Users express high agreement with its excellence across all measured categories. The consolidated assessment is deemed valuable due to its comprehensive and successful nature as an educational resource. It is connected with instructional goals, exhibits logical organization, caters to learners' requirements, and is extremely practical in facilitating enriched and holistic learning experiences.

2. Recommendations for the Improvement of the 3H Session Guide

The MAPEH teachers and futsal coaches offered valuable suggestions to strengthen the 3H Session Guide. One common recommendation was to include more sport-specific drills and practical exercises tailored to futsal's unique demands. As a futsal coach

observed, “The drills are effective but could be improved with more futsal-specific sequences that focus on ball control in small spaces, which is essential in futsal.” Many respondents emphasized the importance of adding sections that address skill progression, allowing players to gradually build their abilities. A Futsal Coach noted, “It would be helpful if the guide included a progression of skills that align with different levels. Some students need foundational drills, while others are ready for more advanced techniques.”

Several coaches also suggested incorporating more detailed explanations of game scenarios to help students understand the sport's tactical elements. “A section on situational drills, like positioning during a power play or managing a tight defense, would be valuable,” one coach commented. They felt that incorporating these scenarios would give students a better grasp of futsal’s strategic side. Another frequent recommendation involved creating a variety of warm-up and cool-down exercises specific to futsal. “Having dynamic stretching routines focused on lower-body flexibility and agility would help prevent injuries and keep the sessions sport-specific,” shared one MAPEH teacher.

3. Recommended Enhancements to the 3H Session Guide

Based on the evaluation results and feedback from MAPEH teachers and futsal coaches, several enhancements to the 3H Session Guide are proposed to further optimize its use and impact. These enhancements draw on the strengths observed in the categories of Adequacy, Coherence, Appropriateness, and Usefulness, as well as specific recommendations for improvement.

3.1 Addition of Futsal-Specific Progression Drills and Advanced Variations

While the guide scored highly for aligning instruction with activities (4.58 WM) and for the effectiveness of its learning activities, coaches suggested enhancing this further by incorporating more futsal-specific drills and tiered progression sequences. By structuring drills to build from foundational to advanced levels, the guide can better accommodate a range of skill levels, allowing students to progressively build competence. As one coach noted, “Adding skill levels to each drill can help us tailor the session for both beginners and those with more experience.”

3.2 Detailed Explanations for Game Scenarios and Tactical Drills

Coherence, with a weighted mean of 4.50, was one of the guide's strengths, especially regarding the alignment of activities with concepts. However, respondents expressed that more situational drills and tactical scenarios unique to futsal—such as managing tight spaces and quick transitions—would enhance understanding and engagement. Including modules on tactical plays and scenarios can strengthen the practical understanding of the sport’s strategy. “More situational practice would help students apply what they’re learning in real game contexts,” shared one MAPEH teacher.

3.3 Customized Warm-Up and Cool-Down Routines Focused on Injury Prevention

The guide's appropriateness scored highly, with respondents appreciating its adaptation to learners and alignment with MELC competencies (4.45 WM). Nonetheless, feedback highlighted the benefit of sport-specific warm-up and cool-down routines, particularly targeting lower-body flexibility and agility, which are crucial in futsal. The addition of these routines would help in injury prevention and prepare students physically for the demands of futsal. A teacher recommended, "Having a set of warm-up exercises specifically designed for agility and flexibility in futsal would be very beneficial."

3.4 Enhanced Visual Aids and Step-by-Step Instructions for Accessibility

The guide's usefulness (4.60 WM) was rated strongly, especially in terms of ease of understanding and serving as an instructional tool. To further support accessibility, adding more graphical aids and breaking down complex drills into clearer steps could help MAPEH teachers unfamiliar with futsal-specific terms. As one teacher noted, "A bit more visual guidance on complex drills would make it easier for teachers who may not be as familiar with futsal to confidently lead sessions."

3.5 Inclusion of an Assessment Module for Skill Tracking

Teachers and coaches emphasized the value of being able to assess and track students' progress over time. While the guide effectively encourages creativity and critical thinking (4.42 WM), an added assessment component would enable educators to measure skill development and highlight areas needing improvement. One futsal coach stated, "An assessment checklist would be helpful to see if students are meeting key skill milestones."

Conclusions

This study aimed to evaluate and enhance the Creative 3H Session Guide through the feedback and experiences of MAPEH teachers and futsal coaches. The findings provide significant insights addressing each of the research questions posed in the Introduction.

1. On the evaluation of the 3H Session Guide's adequacy, coherence, appropriateness, and usefulness, results indicate a consistently high level of satisfaction among respondents, with the guide achieving weighted mean scores in the "Strongly Agree" category across all categories. Teachers and coaches appreciated the guide's clear alignment between instructions and activities, its well-organized structure, and its relevance to learning competencies. The guide was perceived as an effective instructional tool that facilitates both knowledge acquisition and the development of creativity and critical thinking.

2. On the recommendations for improvement, the respondents suggested several key enhancements, including the addition of futsal-specific drills with skill progression levels,

more detailed explanations of game scenarios, and customized warm-up and cool-down routines for futsal. Additional suggestions included providing more visual aids and step-by-step instructions to support teachers unfamiliar with futsal and incorporating an assessment module to help track student progress.

3. On the enhancements needed for the Creative 3H Session Guide, adding sport-specific drills, introducing situational and tactical training modules, creating sport-focused warm-up and cool-down routines, enhancing visual aids for complex drills, and implementing an assessment module are proposed. These adjustments aim to make the 3H Session Guide an even more effective resource for MAPEH teachers and futsal coaches, ensuring it meets the diverse needs of students and supports their skill development in futsal training.

Recommendations

1. Broaden the Application of the 3H Session Guide in Diverse Settings. The findings of this study, which highlight the 3H Session Guide's effectiveness in skill-building and engagement, suggest potential applicability across varied educational and recreational settings. It is recommended that future studies test the guide's adaptability in other districts or with larger sample groups to validate its effectiveness beyond the current setting. Such research could assess whether the guide maintains its coherence, usefulness, and adequacy in different environments or with broader student demographics.

2. Explore the Integration of Digital and Interactive Training Aids. Considering the recommendations for visual aids and step-by-step instructions, future research could explore the impact of digital tools on the training outcomes. An investigation into how these digital aids improve training could provide insights into expanding the guide's effectiveness.

3. Investigate Long-Term Impact on Student Skill Retention and Performance. While the current study demonstrates strong initial effectiveness, further research is necessary to assess the long-term impact of the 3H Session Guide on student athletes' skill retention and performance in futsal.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher affirms that this study was conducted in strict compliance with ethical research standards. Informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to their involvement, ensuring that they were fully aware of the study's purpose, procedures, and their right to withdraw at any time without any consequences. The anonymity and confidentiality of the respondents were rigorously maintained throughout the study, with all identifying information removed to safeguard their privacy and well-being. Additionally, the researcher declares that no conflicts of interest influenced any part of the research process, from data collection to the analysis of findings. Plagiarism was meticulously avoided, and all sources and references were properly acknowledged.

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